

Pseudo-SD: Pseudo Controlled Stable Diffusion for Semi-Supervised and Cross-Domain Semantic Segmentation

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Abstract

Pseudo-labeling is a key technique of semi-supervised and cross-domain semantic segmentation, yet its efficacy is often hampered by the intrinsic noise of pseudo-labels. This study introduces Pseudo-SD, a novel framework that redefines the utilization of pseudo-label knowledge through Stable Diffusion (SD). Our Pseudo-SD innovatively combines pseudo-labels and its text prompts to fine-tune SD models, facilitating the generation of high-quality, diverse synthetic images that closely mimic target data characteristics. Within this framework, two novel mechanisms, i.e., partial attention manipulation, and structured pseudo-labeling, are proposed to effectively spread text-to-image corresponding during SD fine-tuning process and to ensure controllable high-quality image synthesis respectively. Extensive results demonstrate that Pseudo-SD significantly improves the performance on semi-supervised and cross-domain segmentation scenarios. By injecting our Pseudo-SD into current methods, we establish new state-of-the-arts in different datasets, offering a new way for the exploration of effective pseudo-label utilization. The source code is available at <https://github.com/DZhaoxd/Pseudo-SD>.

1. Introduction

Semi-supervised semantic segmentation (SSSS) [15, 40] and cross-domain semantic segmentation [45] (CDSS) aim to train a segmenter with limited or domain-shifted labeled data and abundant unlabeled images, reducing annotation costs. To fully leverage unlabeled data, advanced semi-supervised [13, 28, 57, 59] and cross-domain [6, 12, 52] segmentation methods mainly rely on pseudo-labeling [75]. The core part of this technique is to mitigate noise interference within pseudo-labels [34]. Various methods involving noise regularization, e.g., weak-to-strong consistency [39, 47, 49], data augmentation [12, 42, 62, 64, 72], fea-

Figure 1. Comparison of performance improvements over state-of-the-art (SOTA) **semi-supervised** [57] and **cross-domain** [12, 67] semantic segmentation baselines, in comparison with recent diffusion-based methods for synthetic segmentation data generation [50, 53, 58, 65]. Our method achieves superior performance and demonstrates significant improvements, particularly in the source-free UDA setting, where no real labels are provided.

ture perturbation[24, 44, 46], and denoising pseudo-label [11, 48, 68–70] have been introduced in both fields. However, the effectiveness of training with noisy labels remains uncertain, especially at higher noise rates, limiting their reliability in low-annotation semi-supervised settings and challenging adaptation scenarios. This raises a key question: Instead of directly training on noisy labels, can we better exploit the knowledge in pseudo-labels?

Some pioneering works [3, 18, 40] have leveraged pre-trained GANs to generate samples for SSSS and CDSS without relying on pseudo-labels. However, their effectiveness is limited by the quality of synthesized data. Recently, the Stable Diffusion (SD) model [36, 38] has demonstrated strong generative capabilities, renewing interest in its application to SSSS and CDSS. Advances in using SD for seg-

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Figure 2. Comparison between synthetic images generated by DatasetDM [50] and our Pseudo-SD.

mentation can be broadly categorized into two approaches:

(1) Text-to-Image SD (T2I-SD): These methods extract segmentation masks from diffusion features as labeled synthetic data [50, 53]. However, they struggle to generate task-specific segmentation data, making them less effective for SSSS and CDSS. As shown in Fig. 2, even DatasetDM [50], which fine-tunes SD, tends to generate images dominated by a few semantic categories (e.g., people or vehicles), leading to suboptimal training performance. Compared to real target data, the synthesized images often exhibit significant differences in layout, semantics, and style. (2). Layout-to-Image SD (L2I-SD): These models generate images with precise control using semantic masks as conditions [55, 63]. However, L2I-SD still faces challenges in both SSSS and CDSS. In SSSS, the lack of sufficient mask-image pairs for training L2I leads to degraded generation quality (see Fig. 11). In CDSS, training an L2I model with source domain layouts and images [61] results in images that fail to match the target domain distribution, which is not beneficial in overcoming the domain gap. As shown in Fig. 1, L2I-based methods such as FreeMask [58] and ControlNet [65] fail to achieve satisfactory results. We thus raise the second question: Are there reasonable ways to unleash the potential of SD in SSSS and CDSS?

To address the above questions, we propose Pseudo-SD, a novel framework for SSSS and CDSS that leverages pseudo-label knowledge through Stable Diffusion (SD). The overall pipeline is illustrated in Fig. 3. First, as shown in Fig. 3(a), a segmentation model is trained on a small labeled dataset and then used to generate pseudo labels and text prompts for unlabeled data. Next, in Fig. 3(b), SD is fine-tuned on the target data using reliable pixel pseudo-labels and text prompts to learn domain-specific characteristics. The fine-tuned SD then synthesizes high-quality, diverse images by using structural pseudo-labels as layout control. As shown in Fig. 2, our method generates images with complex layouts, semantics, and task-specific styles.

Figure 3. Schematic of Pseudo-SD. (a) **Train**: A segmentation model is trained using labeled and optionally unlabeled data. (a) **Predict**: The model generates pseudo-labels and pseudo-text prompts. (b) **Train**: SD is fine-tuned using predicted pseudo-text prompts and reliable pixels. (b) **Sampling**: SD synthesizes diverse data controlled by structured pseudo-labels.

Finally, the segmentation model is re-trained on the labeled synthetic images to enhance segmentation performance.

In this process, we introduce the following core designs. First, to inject reliable pseudo-label knowledge into SD during fine-tuning, we propose Partial Attention Manipulation (PAM), which enhances text-to-image cross-attention responses at positions corresponding to reliable pseudo-labels while preserving original responses in uncertain regions. This allows reliable semantics to act as seeds, propagating text-based semantics to surrounding areas. Second, to address generative hallucinations caused by structural distortions in pseudo-labels, we use structured pseudo-labels as spatial conditions for image synthesis. By incorporating unsupervised clustering as a structural prior, we refine pseudo-label layouts to ensure more coherent spatial arrangements, reducing hallucinations. Additionally, we introduce a connected-component removal strategy to filter out distorted regions in synthesized images, further improving quality. Through these efforts, Pseudo-SD significantly enhances the performance in SSSS and CDSS, as shown in Fig. 1. Moreover, it is model-agnostic and can complement existing methods, further boosting their effectiveness.

2. Related Work

Semi-Supervised & Cross-Domain Segmentation Addressing pseudo-label noise in unlabeled target domains is crucial for SSSS and CDSS. In SSSS, CPS [2] and CCT [32] enhance pseudo-label quality via multi-head consistency, while AEL [15], ST++ [56], and AugM [72] reduce noise through strong data perturbations. PerTea [24] and UniMatch [57] further introduce dual- or multi-stream consistency. Recent works explore vision transformers [16, 71] and vision-language models [13] for pseudo-labeling and training. Similarly, in CDSS, methods address error accumulation through pseudo-label selection [19, 29, 33, 76, 77], high-resolution consistency [6], and masked augmenta-

Figure 4. The proportion of reliable pixels (x-axis) and its corresponding accuracy (a, y-axis) and impact on self-training (b, y-axis) across the whole dataset. (c) illustrates a case from (a), where unreliable pixels (in white) are filtered out. The experiments are conducted in a semi-supervised setting with 100 labeled samples on Cityscape.

tions [12]. Our method is compatible with these approaches and can further enhance their performance.

Generative Models for Segmentation. Stable Diffusion (SD) has been explored in segmentation but struggles with SSSS and CDSS. Text-to-image SD, *e.g.*, datasetdm [50] can provide high-quality images and corresponding semantic masks [50, 53], but the lack of task specificity limits its effectiveness [50]. Layout-to-Image SD (L2I-SD), *e.g.*, FreeMask [58], offers better control but suffers from insufficient mask-image pairs in SSSS and fails to generate target-consistent data for CDSS and SSSS. Unlike these approaches, our method focuses on leveraging unlabeled data to drive SD, enabling target data generation under scarce labels, an aspect overlooked by existing methods.

3. Method

Preliminaries. *Semi-supervised semantic segmentation* aims to build a powerful segmentation model using limited labeled data $D_l = \{(x_l^i, y_l^i)\}_{i=1}^{N_l}$ and a large number of unlabeled data $D_u = \{(x_u^i)\}_{i=1}^{N_u}$, where $N_u \gg N_l$. *Cross-domain semantic segmentation* aims to transfer a segmentor trained on the labeled source domain $D_s = \{(x_s^i, y_s^i)\}_{i=1}^{N_s}$ to the unlabeled target domain $D_t = \{(x_t^i)\}_{i=1}^{N_t}$. While the labeled source takes different forms, both tasks share a common objective, leveraging unlabeled data to enhance the segmenter’s performance. State-of-the-art semi-supervised [57] and cross-domain [6] segmentation methods both leverage unlabeled data as,

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_l(x_l, y_l) + \beta \mathcal{L}_u(x_u, \hat{y}_u, \mathcal{M}), \quad (1)$$

where \mathcal{L}_l is the supervised cross-entropy loss, β is the trade-off weight, \mathcal{L}_u is the unsupervised pseudo-labeling loss, \hat{y}_u is the pseudo-label. \mathcal{M} is a binary uncertainty mask of \hat{y}_u where the corresponding uncertainty region is assigned the value 0 and the remainder is 1.

Motivation. To fully utilize unlabeled data, we integrate target knowledge into Stable Diffusion (SD) to synthe-

size task-specific images and semantic masks. We explore whether pseudo-labeled target data can fine-tune SD and find this feasible for two reasons. **First**, pseudo-labels provide relatively accurate category names for text prompt design, enabling the creation of image-text pairs for fine-tuning SD. As shown in Fig. 4(a) and (c), while pixel-level pseudo-labels may not precisely locate spatial positions, they effectively identify image categories. Focusing on high-confidence pixels significantly improves the accuracy of image-level predictions. **Second**, high-confidence pseudo-labeled pixels serve as seeds, providing partial spatial semantics for SD fine-tuning. As illustrated in Fig. 4(a) and (c), retaining high-probability pixels helps refine semantic centers with greater precision. Driven by reliable text prompts and partial spatial semantics, we fine-tune SD on the target and use it as a generative enhancer for segmentation models. As shown in Fig. 4(b), leveraging the same high-confidence ranking pseudo-labels, our Pseudo-SD achieves significantly higher efficiency than the state-of-the-art self-training (ST) method UniMatch [57].

3.1. Pseudo-Label Guided Fine-Tuning

With reliable text prompts, a straightforward approach for fine-tuning is using ControlNet [65], where reliable partial semantics in pseudo-labels serve as spatial control, and an adapter is trained to influence SD generation. However, adding control signals struggles to effectively diffuse local spatial semantics into the global context, leading to severe artifacts and unrealistic textures during sampling (Visual examples provided in Appendix E).

Some advanced image editing methods [1, 8, 10] achieve text-controlled editing by modifying the text-image cross-attention maps during the inverse diffusion process, as these maps localize the semantic spatial positions of the generated images. Inspired by this, we propose manipulating partial attention responses using reliable pixel-level pseudo-labels as coarse-grained semantic guidance for fine-tuning

Figure 5. Pseudo-SD: pipeline of fine-tuning stable diffusion model and synthesizing high-quality images using pseudo-labels.

SD. The pipeline is illustrated in Fig. 5(a).

Cross-Attention Extraction. Given target sample x , its pseudo-label \hat{y} and corresponding uncertainty mask \mathcal{M} , we define the pixel-level reliable pseudo-label as \hat{y}_r , *i.e.*, the set of pixels in \hat{y} corresponding to positions with a value of 0 in \mathcal{M} . Then, we formulate its corresponding pseudo text prompts $p = \{p_1, \dots, p_N\}$ by retrieving the name of the category in the reliable pseudo-label \hat{y}_r , where N is the category number of the reliable pseudo-label \hat{y}_r . Stable Diffusion (SD) aims to denoise the noisy latent state z_T into a clean latent state z_0 , containing the semantics of the provided text prompt p . For each layer of the denoising U-Net in SD, the cross-attention are built independently between each position of the latent state z_t and each token of the text embedding, *i.e.*,

$$\mathcal{A}_t = \text{softmax} \frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d}} \in \mathbb{R}^{W \times H \times N}, \quad (2)$$

where $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{W \times H \times C}$ is the query of z_t , $K \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times C}$ is the key of the text embedding $\rho(p)$, and d is the scaling factor of feature dimension. W, H, C are the height, width, and channels of latent state z_t . ρ is the pre-trained text encoder. As observed by [10, 55], the text-image cross-attention map \mathcal{A}_t locates the semantic spatial positions of the clean latent state z_0 .

Partial Attention Manipulation. We manipulate the spatial response of the cross-attention map \mathcal{A}_t with reliable pseudo-labels. For reliable areas represented by \mathcal{M} , we use the semantic of \hat{y}_r as class responses to manipulate the attention activation of the corresponding locations of cross attention map \mathcal{A}_t ; For unreliable areas, we retain original attention of \mathcal{A}_t . Specifically, we form the pseudo-label \hat{y} as N -way one-hot format $\hat{y}_{oh} \in \mathbb{R}^{W \times H \times N}$, the manipulation

are performed as follows,

$$\mathcal{A}_{mt} = \mathcal{A}_t(1 - \mathcal{M}) + \hat{y}_{oh}\mathcal{M}. \quad (3)$$

Through this operation, text embeddings are controlled to influence the semantics of specified spatial locations, where supervision of text-to-image mapping is reliable, and these regions act like seeds to guide SD to learn the semantics of other regions. Since the cross-attention maps in SD have different resolutions on each layer, we perform Eq. (3) by up- (down-) sampling the pseudo labels \hat{y} and uncertainty mask \mathcal{M} to the corresponding resolution of that layer.

Fine-Tuning. With manipulated attention, we fix the text encoder, and fine-tune the denoising U-Net to learn the visual distribution of the target image, following the same objective of SD in the pre-train stage [36],

$$L = E_{t, z_0, \epsilon} [\|\epsilon_\theta(z_t, \hat{y}, \rho(p), t) - \epsilon\|_2^2]. \quad (4)$$

3.2. Pseudo-Label Controlled Sampling

During fine-tuning, we use category names as text prompts, which do not provide a complete layout semantics like complete sentences. Therefore, during sampling, only using pseudo-text-prompts makes it difficult to generate target-specific scenes and their semantic masks (see Appendix E for visualization). To this end, we propose to utilize pseudo-labels as layout controls to sample images with specific layouts through full attention manipulation. The pipeline is shown in Fig. 5(b).

Full Attention Manipulation. A simple way is to employ complete pseudo-labels \hat{y} as spatial conditions to manipulate the full attention map, *i.e.*, modify the Eq. (3) as $\mathcal{A}'_{mt} = \hat{y}_{oh}$. However, we observe that most complete pseudo-labels are poorly structured, embodying aliasing of

Figure 6. Observations on generative hallucinations: Poorly structured pseudo-labels (a) cause the illusion in (b), while structured ones (c) alleviate it, as shown in (d).

object category boundaries, which can easily lead to generative hallucinations as shown in Fig. 6. We analyzed that this is due to the poor connectivity structure altering the object’s properties, confusing the diffusion model.

Structured Pseudo-Labels. We propose to enhance the structuring of the complete pseudo-labels \hat{y} to alleviate this problem. We found that unsupervised semantic segmentation (USS) methods can better capture object contours and shape structures because they are not constrained by specific given semantics. Although they may suffer from over-segmentation problems, they can serve as a structural enhancer to improve the structure of pseudo-labels. Driven by this, we turn to the segmented structure of USS methods [9, 31] to complete the structure of pseudo-labels within connected regions, as shown in Fig. 7. Structured pseudo-labels control the generation of images with better visual effects that match their semantics, as shown in Fig. 6(c) and (d). It is important to note that structured pseudo-labels can amplify semantic noise. As seen in Fig. 6(a), (b), and (c), the original pseudo-label incorrectly classifies ‘train’ as ‘bus’, and the structured pseudo-labels worsen this error. Training directly with structured pseudo-labels could lead to even greater interference. However, our method generates images that semantically align with the pseudo-labels, avoiding this issue. More quantitative results supporting this claim are presented in Table 6.

3.3. Efficient Synthetic Data Utilization

The next challenge is how to better utilize synthesized data to benefit segmentation models.

Connected Components Removal. Although the quality of synthesized images has improved using structured pseudo-labels, we still notice some structural noise in localized connected regions, as shown in Fig. 8(a) and (b). This noise can hinder the effectiveness of semantic segmentation models trained on synthetic data. To address this, we propose removing noisy connected regions based on a simple principle: if a trained segmentation model cannot recognize a connected region, it should be removed. Specifically, we use predictions from segmentation models trained on limited samples or source domain data to make this judgment.

Figure 7. Schematic diagram of structuring pseudo-labels: The yellow-highlighted connected regions are obtained by an unsupervised segmentation model [9].

Figure 8. Visualizing the removal of connected components with distorted semantics. We use “synthetic label” instead of “structured pseudo-label” as mentioned above to avoid confusion. See the Appendix E for more visualizations.

If the model fails to predict the designated synthetic category for a connected region, that region will be filtered out. As shown in Fig. 8, this approach not only eliminates distorted semantics but also preserves intact regions, allowing segmentation models to learn more challenging semantics.

Hard-Adapted Class Resampling. While SD allows us to generate unlimited data to improve model performance, it comes with increased training costs. To balance this, we propose resampling hard-to-adapt classes to create more valuable samples, which can enhance segmentation models. In SSSS and CDSS tasks, adapting to minority classes [15, 42] is particularly challenging. To this end, we resample pseudo-labels containing minority categories as control conditions and generate more diverse images with these categories. Specifically, we calculate the frequency of each category in the pseudo-labels of all unlabeled data and use the inverse of this frequency as the sampling rate for that category. See the Appendix C for details.

Training with Synthetic Data. With synthesized data, we treat them as labeled data and incorporate them into existing semi-supervised or cross-domain segmentation methods. Subsequently, we continue training the segmentation model with all these data to enhance its performance.

Discussion on unfair comparisons. Concerns may arise regarding the fairness of comparing our SD-based method with existing approaches that do not incorporate diffusion models. However, our primary goal is to explore SD’s potential in SSSS and CDSS, an area rarely studied. More-

Pascal	1/115 (92)	1/58 (183)	1/29 (366)	1/14 (732)	1/7 (1464)	Cityscapes	1/64(46)	1/32 (100)	1/16 (186)	1/8 (372)	1/4 (744)	1/2 (1488)
U2PL [48]	68.0	69.2	73.7	76.2	79.5	PCR [54]	-	-	73.4	76.3	78.4	79.1
PS-MT [24]	65.8	69.6	76.6	78.4	80.0	U2PL [48]	-	-	74.9	76.5	78.5	79.1
PCR [54]	70.1	74.7	77.2	78.5	80.7	ESL [26]	-	-	75.1	77.2	78.9	80.5
UniMatch [57]	75.2	77.2	78.8	79.9	81.2	3-CPS [20]	-	-	75.7	77.4	78.5	-
3-CPS[20]	75.7	77.7	80.1	80.9	82.0	UniMatch [57]	65.4	73.0	76.6	77.9	79.2	79.5
AllSpark [43]	76.1	78.4	79.7	80.7	82.1	AllSpark [43]	-	-	78.3	79.2	80.5	81.4
CorrMatch [41]	76.4	78.5	79.4	80.6	-	CorrMatch[41]	-	-	77.3	78.5	79.4	80.4
Pseudo-SD [Ours]	78.9	79.2	80.7	81.9	82.7	Pseudo-SD [Ours]	69.8	76.1	78.5	79.5	80.5	81.5

Table 1. Comparison with state-of-the-art methods on Pascal and Cityscapes with ResNet-101.

COCO	1/512 (232)	1/256 (463)	1/128 (925)	1/64 (1849)	1/32 (3697)	ADE20K	1/64 (316)	1/32 (632)	1/16 (1263)	1/8 (2526)
PC2Seg [73]	29.9	37.5	39.9	43.7	46.1	PC2Seg [73]	-	26.8	28.1	33.4
UniMatch [57]	31.9	38.9	44.4	48.2	49.8	AEL[15]	-	28.4	33.2	38.0
LogicDiag [21]	33.1	40.3	45.4	48.8	50.5	UniMatch[57]	21.1	28.8	30.9	35.0
AllSpark [43]	34.1	41.6	45.4	49.5	50.9	AllSpark[43]	-	-	32.7	36.3
Pseudo-SD	39.9	44.8	48.2	50.2	51.9	Pseudo-SD [Ours]	28.1	33.3	35.2	39.3

Table 2. Comparison with state-of-the-art methods on COCO with Xception-65 [4] and ADE20K with ResNet-101.

UDA: GTA→Cityscapes		UDA: SYNTHIA→Cityscapes		SFUDA: GTA→Cityscapes		SFUDA: SYNTHIA→Cityscapes	
Methods	mIoU	Methods	mIoU	Methods	mIoU	Methods	mIoU
DAFormer [14]	68.3	DAFormer [14]	60.9	DTST [67]	55.4	DTST [67]	50.7
HRDA [6]	73.8	HRDA [6]	65.8	VPT [27]	56.2	VPT [27]	52.6
Rtea [68]	74.7	Rtea [68]	66.5	CROTS [25]	53.7	CROTS [25]	51.3
MIC [12]	75.9	MIC [12]	67.3	Cross-match [60]	57.7	Cross-match [60]	55.6
Pseudo-SD [Ours]	77.0	Pseudo-SD [Ours]	68.1	Pseudo-SD [Ours]	62.9	Pseudo-SD [Ours]	60.2

Table 3. Cross-domain semantic segmentation performance. Detailed IoU scores of each category are in the Appendix C.

over, our method is integrative, enhancing rather than competing with existing pseudo-labeling techniques (see Table 4). Generative models have previously been used to improve SSSS, as seen in [3, 18], where pre-trained GANs generated new samples to enhance performance. However, as stronger learning-based SSSS methods emerged, augmentation-based approaches became less effective due to the limited quality of synthetic data. We believe our work offers a novel perspective on leveraging large-scale pre-trained diffusion models to address SSSS and CDSS challenges.

4. Experimental Results

Datasets and Tasks. **Task-I:** COCO [22], Pascal-VOC [7], ADE20K [74] and Cityscapes [5] are used to evaluate Pseudo-SD in semi-supervised semantic segmentation tasks. In addition to traditional labeled data partitioning protocols, we also explore fewer labeled data partitions in these datasets. **Task-II:** GTA5 [35], SYNTHIA [37], and Cityscapes [5] are used for evaluating Pseudo-SD in cross-domain semantic segmentation tasks, *i.e.*, GTA5→Cityscapes (G2C), SYNTHIA→Cityscapes (S2C). In addition to mainstream Unsupervised Domain Adaptation (UDA) tasks, we also explore our method under Source-Free UDA (SFUDA) [23, 51].

4.1. Implementation Details (Appendix B)

4.2. Comparison with State-of-the-Art Methods

Task-I: Semi-Supervised Semantic Segmentation. Our Pseudo-SD is compared with SOTA semi-supervised meth-

ods on four benchmarks in Tables 1-2.

Pascal VOC 2012. Table 1 compares the performance of Pseudo-SD with previous methods across various labeled data subsets, ranging from 1/115 (92 labels) to 1/7 (1,464 labels) of the training set. Pseudo-SD significantly outperforms existing methods, improving upon the SOTA method UniMatch by +1.7% mIoU with 1,464 labels and +2.5% with 92 labels. The more pronounced improvements with fewer labels suggest that Pseudo-SD is more effective at leveraging unlabeled data.

Cityscapes. Cityscapes features many small-size categories, like poles and traffic signs, as well as confusing categories such as trains and trams, which adds complexity to semi-supervised learning. Despite these challenges, Table 1 demonstrates that our approach still achieves performance improvements ranging from 1.1% (with 1,488 labels) to 4.7% (with 46 labels) in this setting.

MS COCO. COCO [22] comprises 118k training images annotated with 81 categories, making semi-supervised learning particularly challenging. Evaluating this dataset better reflects the effectiveness of utilizing unlabeled data. As shown in Table 2, our Pseudo-SD significantly outperforms all existing methods, with improvements ranging from 2.6% (with 3,697 labels) to 9.7% (with 232 labels).

ADE20K. We adopt the experimental settings from [15] and provide additional semi-supervised segmentation results on the ADE20K dataset [74], as detailed in Table 2. Our method outperforms UniMatch by 7.8%, 4.8%, 4.6%, and 4.6% under the data protocols of 1/64, 1/32, 1/16, and 1/8, respectively.

Task-II: Cross-Domain Semantic Segmentation. We

Methods	Pascal (92)	Cityscapes (46)	COCO (232)	ADE20K (316)	Methods	UDA-G2C	UDA-S2C	Methods	SFUDA-G2C	SFUDA-S2C
ST++ [56]	65.2	61.4	25.6	15.9	ProDA (R101) [66]	53.7	51.9	HCL [17] (R101)	48.1	43.5
+ Ours	74.9	67.7	35.9	23.7	+ Ours	61.1	58.7	+ Ours	56.1	52.9
Unimatch [57]	75.2	65.4	31.9	21.1	DaFormer(MiT)	68.2	60.9	DTST [67] (R101)	55.4	50.7
+ Ours	79.6	70.1	40.6	28.9	+ Ours	72.9	67.4	+ Ours	60.1	54.9
SemiVL [13] (ViT-B)	84.0	68.9	50.1	33.7	HRDA (MiT)	73.8	65.8	DaFormer(MiT) [14]	59.6	55.2
+ Ours	84.6	71.2	51.1	34.2	+ Ours	75.0	66.6	+ Ours	63.8	59.9

Table 4. Results of combining Pseudo-SD and different semi-supervised and cross-domain semantic segmentation methods.

Figure 9. Comparison with other Stable Diffusion based data synthesis methods for semantic segmentation tasks, *i.e.*, Dataset Diffusion [30] and Datasetdm [50].

Figure 10. (a) and (b): Ablation studies on Fine-Tuning (FT) SD with different forms of data. (c): Ablation studies on sampling SD using different semantic masks as conditions.

compare Pseudo-SD with other methods on multiple cross-domain benchmarks in Table 3.

GTA5 → Cityscapes. The GTA5 dataset [35] has 24,966 images with a resolution of 1914×1052, sharing 19 categories with Cityscapes. Pseudo-SD achieves 1.1% improvement over the SOTA UDA method MIC [12], bringing it closer to the upper bound by fully using labeled target data. In the more challenging task of source-free UDA, Pseudo-SD achieves an additional 5.3% improvement, demonstrating the effectiveness in leveraging unlabeled data.

SYNTHIA → Cityscapes. The SYNTHIA dataset [37] has 9,400 images with 1280×720 resolution, sharing 16 categories with Cityscapes. The domain gap of this task is deeper, including in imaging perspective and rendering technology. Our Pseudo-SD still achieves significant improvements similar to the above tasks in both settings, improving performance by 1.3% and 5.3% respectively.

4.3. Analysis & Ablation Studies

Combine Pseudo-SD with Other Methods. Table 4 demonstrates that our method can be plug-and-played into various semi-supervised and domain adaptation methods, significantly enhancing their performance. Even with the inclusion of the stronger SemiVL baseline in SSSS and HRDA in CDSS, our method still achieves significant performance gains. This illustrates the model-agnostic nature of our method.

Is it necessary to fine-tune the Stable Diffusion (SD) on

the target data? Yes, we validate this claim further in Fig. 9, where we compare advanced methods [30, 50] that utilize pre-trained SD with a few labeled data to enhance segmentation tasks. The comparison shows that these methods either fail to improve or even degrade the performance of semi-supervised and cross-domain segmentation models, particularly on the complex Cityscape dataset. In contrast, our method achieves a significant performance boost, demonstrating the importance of fine-tuning SD for synthesizing task-specific images.

Is it feasible to fine-tune SD on small amounts of labeled data in semi-supervised segmentation? Fig. 10(a) and (b) show that fine-tuning SD using a small amount of labeled data only brings very weak performance improvements. This shows that the few-sample-driven SD generation is full of challenges. In contrast, our proposed fine-tuning SD on pseudo-labeled data achieves greater performance gains, especially in very limited labeled data.

Using the labeled (source) semantic mask as the control for synthesizing images. Fig. 10(c) shows that this alternative method results in only a slight improvement due to the restricted layout. In contrast, our structured pseudo-labels offer a richer semantic layout, leading to more noticeable gains. In addition, on both UDA tasks, we explored using only the source domain semantic mask as layout control, which showed limited gains. This is because the spatial layout differences between domains cause a slight domain shift in the synthesized images, limiting its effectiveness.

Figure 11. Comparison the synthetic image by ours and ControlNet [65] using the structured pseudo-labels under the semi-supervised 100 labeled data task.

Details and visualization of ControlNet’s [65] results with pseudo-labeled data. Fig. 11 shows that for ControlNet, it is difficult to efficiently fine-tune the added adapter using pseudo-control, resulting in severe artifacts and unrealistic textures in the sampled data. In contrast, our method can achieve more efficient fine-tuning of stable diffusion, thereby generating higher quality samples during sampling. **Effectiveness of Partial Attention Manipulation.** Table 5 shows that manipulating the text-image cross-attention map with pseudo-labels is more effective for adapting to SD in data-scarce scenarios compared to using ControlNet [65] with pseudo-labels. Moreover, injecting only reliable pseudo-labels provides greater benefits to the segmenter than using all pseudo-labels for attention manipulation, further supporting the rationale behind our method.

Effectiveness of Synthesizing Images with Structured Pseudo-Labels (SPL). We explore two aspects: the impact of using SPL alone on segmentation models and the effect of combining SPL with our approach. We use two unsupervised semantic segmentation (USS) methods, STEGO [9] and U2Seg [31], as structural enhancers. As shown in Table 6: (1) Using SPL alone does not significantly improve performance, even with additional model distillation [66]. (2) While using original pseudo-labels for synthesized images provides initial improvements, incorporating SPL yields even greater benefits. This indicates that SPL alone does not lead to substantial gains for segmentation models, but when combined with our method, it does.

Methods	Semi-Supervised Task			Cross-Domain Task	
	Pascal (1/115)	COCO (1/512)	Cityscapes (1/64)	SFUDA (R-101)	UDA (HRDA)
Baseline	75.2	31.9	65.4	55.6	75.8
All PL for CN	69.2	27.6	60.4	39.6	50.4
Reliable PL for CN	70.9	30.5	63.9	51.5	65.8
All PL for AM	74.9	34.6	66.7	58.7	74.9
Reliable PL for PAM	79.1	39.9	69.8	62.7	76.9

Table 5. Ablation on fine-tuning SD with Pseudo-Labels (PL) using ControlNet [65] (CN) and our Partial Attention Manipulation (PAM).

Method	Semi-supervised Task			Cross-domain Task	
	Pascal (1/115)	COCO (1/512)	Cityscapes (1/64)	SFUDA (R-101)	UDA (HRDA)
Baseline	75.2	31.9	65.4	55.6	75.8
PL-STEGO	73.3	30.1	62.8	52.7	72.9
PL-U2Seg	73.1	33.1	63.4	55.3	73.9
PL-STEGO+KD	73.8	34.9	64.1	56.3	74.2
Ours+ PL	78.4	36.6	68.1	60.7	76.1
Ours+PL-STEGO	77.8	38.1	68.4	62.1	76.2
Ours+PL-U2Seg	79.1	39.9	69.8	62.7	76.9
w/o HCR	77.9	37.1	67.1	59.7	75.9
w/o CCR	74.9	35.6	66.2	56.7	75.2

Table 6. Ablation experiment on the proposed module. “PL-STEGO/U2Seg” means using unsupervised segmentation method STEGO [9] and U2Seg [31] for structuring PL. KD means knowledge distillation in [66]. CCR is our Connected Components Removal. HCR is our Hard-Adapted Class Resampling.

Effectiveness of Filtering and Sampling Strategies. Table 6 highlights the significant benefits of CCR and HCR. Specifically, in tasks where the initial segmentation model struggles, such as the semi-supervised task on the COCO dataset and the SFUDA task, our CCR proves particularly effective. This suggests that in these scenarios, the SD model is more affected by semantic noise. Additionally, in scenarios dealing with class-imbalance target data, *e.g.*, Cityscapes, and COCO, CCR leads to even greater performance improvements.

More Evaluation. Additional details, including parameter analysis, visualizations, and limitation & failure cases, are provided in Appendices D, E, and F, respectively.

5. Conclusion

We introduce Pseudo-SD, a novel framework that uses pseudo-labels to improve semi-supervised semantic segmentation. By incorporating reliable pseudo-labels into the stable diffusion model, Pseudo-SD generates task-specific images and corresponding semantic masks, enhancing segmentation learning with these synthesized images as augmented data. Extensive experiments show that Pseudo-SD significantly improves performance in various semi-supervised and cross-domain segmentation tasks. We believe this approach can inspire new methods for using pseudo-labels in label-efficient segmentation.

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